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**THE STUDY OF *SHEETALI KUMBHAKA* AND ITS ROLE IN HEALTH AND
DISEASE AS DESCRIBED IN *YOGIC LITERATURE***

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Abstract

Yoga is a Life Science, envisaged for the spiritual upliftment of self, where, benefit in the condition of health is a byproduct. *Yoga* comprises of eight limbs i.e., *Yama, Niyama, Asana, Pranayama, Pratyahara, Dharana, Dhyana, and Samadhi*. 'Prana' and 'Ayama' are the two words that make up the word *Pranayama*. It is psychosomatic, since it explores the intimate relationship between the body and mind. *Pranayama* utilizes vital energy to influence the flow of *Prana* in the *Nadis*, or energy channels, of the *Pranayama Kosha*, or energy body, and is practiced to gain control over the *Prana* and attain the ultimate spiritual goal of *Moksha*. *Sheetali kumbhaka* is an important type of *Ashtakumbhakas*. It cools down the body and reduces mental & emotional excitation and encourages the free flow of *Prana* throughout the body. For fulfilling the goal, all available classical *Yogic* literature viz., *Bhagavad-Gita, Vasishtha Samhita, Shiva Samhita, Hatha Yoga Pradipika, Hatharatnavali, Hathatatvakaumudi, Gheranda Samhita, Upnishat* and selected Contemporary books have been thoroughly referred for compiling reference about *Sheetali kumbhaka*, it's technique, benefits, time of practice, safety, contraindications and adverse effects. It is also aimed to explore the practice of *Sheetali Kumbhaka* in different *Vyadhi* with the help of *Yogic* texts. This study provides a comprehensive overview of *Sheetali kumbhaka* as described in *Yogic* literature and along with its potential in promoting holistic health.

Key Words:

Pranayama, Sheetali kumbhaka, Yoga

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INTRODUCTION:

Yogashastra is one of the ancient sciences gaining acceptance worldwide in the current era. *Yogic* practices comprise various types of *Asanas*, *Pranayama*, *Bandha*, *Mudra*, *Shatkarma*, etc. *Pranayama* is one of them, as described in many classical *Yogic* texts. 'Prana' and 'Ayama' are the two words that make up the word *Pranayama*. *Prana* means vital energy or life force, and *Ayama* means restraint, prolongation or control. *Pranayama* thus means the prolongation of breath and its restraint¹. *Pranayama* utilizes breathing to influence the flow of *Prana* in the *Nadis* or energy channels of the *Pranamaya Kosha* or energy body. The techniques of *Pranayama* provide the method whereby the life force can be activated and regulated in order to go beyond one's normal boundaries or limitations and attain a higher state of vibratory energy and awareness. It consists of a long, sustained subtle flow of inhalation (*Puraka*), retention of breath (*Kumbhaka*), and exhalation (*Rechaka*).

Kumbhaka is the most important aspect of *Pranayama*. The breath can either be held internally or externally. External retention is known as *Bahiranga Kumbhaka*, and internal retention is *Antaranga Kumbhaka*. These both forms of *Kumbhaka* are performed consciously by control of the breath. *Kumbhaka-Paddhati* explains fifty-seven types of *Kumbhaka* with forty-seven stages². *Gheranda Samhita*³ and *Hatha Pradipika*⁴ have explained *Ashtakumbhakas*. *Sheetali Kumbhaka* is an important type of *Ashtakumbhakas*.

Sheetali Kumbhaka means 'Cooling breath'. This practice of *Kumbhaka* has a calming and soothing effect on the body. However, this practice not only cools and calms the physical body but also affects the mind in the same way.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

- 1) The present work is aimed to understand the concept of *Sheetali Kumbhaka*, its technique, benefits, time of practice, safety, contraindications, and adverse effects.
- 2) It is also aimed to explore the practice of *Sheetali Kumbhaka* in different *Vyadhi* with the help of *Yogic* texts.
- 3) To know how the *Sheetali Kumbhaka* acts and influences an individual's physical, mental, and spiritual well-being.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All available classical *Yogic* literature, viz., *Upanishat*, *Bhagavad Geeta*, *Vasishtha Samhita*, *Shiva Samhita*, *Hatha Pradipika*, *Gheranda Samhita*, *Hatharatnavali*, *Hathatattvakaumudi*, and selected Contemporary books have been thoroughly reviewed for the current paper on the concept of *Sheetali Kumbhaka*. Different databases, such as PubMed, Research Gate, Google Scholar, Science Direct, and J-Gate, were also searched using keywords like *Yoga*, *Pranayama*, and *Sheetali Kumbhaka* with the help of Boolean operators like "AND", "OR," and "Not". Among these, research papers and articles have been reviewed.

RESULT

The concept of *Pranayama* has been described in ancient literature like the *Vedas*, *Upanishadas*, *Bhagavad-Geeta*, *Hatha* texts, and selected Contemporary books. The word *Kumbhaka* is derived from the word *Kumbha*, meaning a water pot. Just as a water pot contains water, similarly, when the lungs hold the air, it is called *Kumbhaka*. *Kumbhaka* is also a synonym of *Pranayama* and has been profusely used in the *Puranika* and *Hathyogic* literature.

Classical references of *Kumbhaka* and *Sheetali Kumbhaka*:

Sr. No.	Name of Samhita	<i>Kumbhaka</i>	<i>Sheetali Kumbhaka</i>
1.	<i>Hamsa Upnishat</i>	×	×
2.	<i>Amritbindu Upnishat</i>	×	×
3.	<i>Kshurika Upnishat</i>	×	×
4.	<i>Tejobindu Upnishat</i>	✓	×
5.	<i>Nadabindu Upnishat</i>	×	×
6.	<i>Dhyana bindu Upnishat</i>	✓	×
7.	<i>Yogatattva Upnishat</i>	✓	×
8.	<i>Trishikhibrahmana Upnishat</i>	✓	×
9.	<i>Mandala brahman Upnishat</i>	✓	×
10.	<i>Advyayataraka Upnishat</i>	×	×
11.	<i>Shandilya Upnishat</i>	✓	×
12.	<i>Yogashikha Upnishat</i>	✓	✓
13.	<i>Pashupatabrahma Upnishat</i>	×	×
14.	<i>Yoga-kundalini Upnishat</i>	✓	✓
15.	<i>Jabala Darshana</i>	✓	×

16.	<i>Amrutanad Upnishat</i>	✓	×
17.	<i>Vasishtha Samhita</i>	✓	×
18.	<i>Shiva Samhita,</i>	✓	✓
19.	<i>Hatha Pradipika</i>	✓	✓
20.	<i>Gheranda Samhita</i>	✓	✓
21.	<i>Hatharatnavali</i>	✓	✓
22.	<i>Hathatattvakaumudi</i>	✓	✓

For the practices of *Pranayama*, it is essential to follow certain rules. Many texts have mentioned the technique of *Pranayama*.

आदौ स्थानं तथा कालं मिताहारं तथापरम्।

नाडीशुद्धिं ततः पश्चात्प्राणायामं च साधयेत् ॥2॥ - (घे. सं. 5/2)

Initially, an appropriate location for the practice of *Pranayama* should be selected. Subsequently, a consistent time should be established, and suitable dietary arrangements should be made to support the practice. Once the place, time, and diet are properly regulated, purification of the *Nadis* should be undertaken prior to commencing *Pranayama*.

PLACE FOR THE PRACTICE

सुदेशे धार्मिके राज्ये सुभिक्षे निरुपद्रवे ।

कृत्वा तत्रैकं कुटीरं प्राचीरैः परिवेष्टितम् ॥5॥

.....
एवं स्थानेषु गुप्तेषु प्राणायामं समभ्यसेत् ॥7॥ - (घे. सं. 5/5-7)

Yogic practices are ideally conducted in a serene and spiritually conducive environment, characterized by the availability of food and the absence of internal or external disturbances. In such a location, a simple dwelling should be established, enclosed within a boundary for privacy and protection. Access to a reliable water source, such as a well, is essential. The chosen site should be level, neither

elevated nor depressed, and the ground traditionally prepared, often with a natural plaster such as cow dung, to promote cleanliness and sanctity. The location should be secluded and free from noise and other distractions to support focused practice. *Kumbhaka* should be done in a clean, airy place, free from insects. The practice of *Kumbhaka* should not be done in a far-off place, in a forest, in a capital city, or in a crowd, otherwise, there will be less *Siddhi*, a lack of success.

TIME FOR THE PRACTICE

प्रातर्मध्यन्दिने सायमर्धरात्रे च कुम्भकान् ।

शनैरशीतिपर्यन्तं चतुर्वारं समभ्यसेत् ॥ - (त्रि. ब्रा. उ. १००)

According to the *Trishikhi Brahmana Upnishat*, *Kumbhaka* should be practised four times a day, in the early morning, afternoon, evening and midnight, with 80 cycles at a time.

Yogic practices are traditionally not initiated during the *Hemanta* (early winter), *Shishira* (late winter), *Grishma* (summer), and *Varsha* (monsoon) seasons, as beginning practice in these periods is believed to increase susceptibility to illness⁵. Instead, it is recommended that practice commence during the *Vasanta* (spring) and *Sharada* (autumn) seasons, which are considered more conducive to health and are traditionally associated with greater success and reduced risk of disease. *Sheetali* cools the body and should therefore be practised during warm seasons is more benefitted. It can even be done at night during summer months, especially for therapeutic benefits. One can do this practice of *Kumbhaka* under proper guidance and supervision.

PROPER DIET

According to the *Hatha Pradipika*, a practitioner who engages in *Kumbhaka* (breath retention) without appropriate dietary regulation is prone to various illnesses. Therefore, the importance of being a *Mitahari* - one who consumes a moderate diet. This is defined as unctuous food (*Snigdha*), sweet (*Madhura*), consumed in a quantity that fills three-fourths of the stomach, with the remaining one-fourth left empty, and taken with the attitude of offering it as a devotional act to please *Shiva*⁶. A practitioner should eat food prepared from *Shali* (Rice), *Yava* (Barley), or *Godhuma* (Wheat) and pulses like *Mudga* (Green gram), *Masha* (Black gram), *Chanaka* (Chickpea), etc, which have been cleaned. *Patola* (Pointed gourd), *Surana* (Elephant yam), *Kakkolam* (Sponge gourd), *Karkati* (cucumber), *Dumbharim* (Fig), *Kantakantakam* (Jack fruit), *Vartaki* (Indian Nightshade), *Mulaka* (Radish), and *Shaka* like *Balashaka*, *Kalashaka*, *Patolapatra*, *Panchashaka*, are also suitable. Food intake should be moderate; traditionally, it is advised that half the stomach be filled with solid food, one-quarter with water, and the remaining quarter left empty to facilitate proper air circulation and digestion⁷.

When commencing practice, one should avoid *Katu*, *Amla*, *Lavana*, *Tikta Rasa*, *Dadhi* (Curd), *Takra* (Buttermilk), *Madya* (Alcohol), *Tal* (Palm nuts), and *Panas* (jack fruit). Consuming foods such as

Kulattha (Horse gram), *Masura* (Lentils), *Kushmand* (White gourd), *Shaka dandaka* (Vegetable stems), *Tumbi* (Gourd), *Kola* (Berry), *Kapittha* (Wood apple), etc., is prohibited. *Kathina* (Hard), *Paryushita* (Stale), *Ati-Ushna* (Extremely hot), and *Ati-Shita* (Extremely cold) foods should be avoided. Irregular eating habits such as consuming only one meal per day, prolonged fasting, or frequent snacking between meals are discouraged. Foods that contribute to the accumulation of *Ama* (toxins) or that undergo putrefaction within the gastrointestinal tract should be strictly avoided, as they are believed to disrupt physiological and energetic balance. From the yogic perspective, food is to be regarded as a form of medicine, consumed with awareness and discipline, to purify the body, stabilize the mind, and support both the sustenance of life and the advancement of *Sadhana* (spiritual practice).

PURIFICATION OF NADIS

The practice of *Kumbhaka* (breath retention) is fundamentally concerned with regulating the flow of *Prana* within the body and facilitating *Pranic* awakening. However, the unimpeded movement and activation of *Prana* can only occur when the *Nadis*, the subtle energy channels, are free from blockages. According to *Sage Gheranda*, this preparatory process, known as *Nadi Shuddhi* (purification of the *Nadis*), is essential prior to the initiation of *Kumbhaka* practice. The purification of these channels not only allows for the free flow of vital energy but also aids in the removal of various gross and subtle obstructions that may hinder yogic progress.

TECHNIQUE OF SHEETALI KUMBHAKA

Technique 1

1. The Practitioner should assume a stable and comfortable meditative posture, preferably *Padmasana* (Lotus pose), *Siddhasana* (Adept's pose), *Swastikasana* (Auspicious pose) or *Virasana* (Hero's pose), which are conducive to prolonged practice and facilitate physical and mental steadiness.
2. The hands should be placed on the knees in either *Jnana Mudra* or *Chin Mudra*, both of which are traditional hand gestures used to promote concentration and facilitate the inward flow of awareness during meditative and respiratory practices.
3. The practitioner should sit in stillness for a period of time, maintaining a firm alignment of the back and spinal column. With the eyes closed, the practitioner should consciously relax the entire body to cultivate a state of physical and mental relaxation.
4. The practitioner should maintain a steady head position and extend the tongue outward as far as possible, without causing strain. The sides of the tongue should then be curled upwards to form a tube-like shape. Air should be drawn in through the tongue, akin to using a straw, allowing the abdomen to fill with air during the inhalation process.
5. Upon completing a full inhalation, the practitioner should withdraw the tongue and close the mouth.

6. Following this, the practitioner should lower the head and perform *Jalandhar Bandha* (chin lock). During this practice, the breath should be held (*Kumbhaka*) according to the individual's capacity.
7. The breath is then exhaled through the nose, and a sensation of coolness may be felt on the tongue and the roof of the mouth. This marks one complete round of the practice.

Technique 2

The *Sheetali Kumbhaka* should be practised appropriate control over the duration of inhalation, retention, and exhalation. Initially, practitioners should follow a balanced ratio of 1:1:1 for these phases. Once this becomes comfortable, the duration of inhalation, retention, and exhalation can be gradually extended to a ratio of 1:2:2, and eventually to 1:4:2.⁸

DURATION

प्रथमे दिवसे कार्यं कुम्भकानां चतुष्टयम्।

प्रत्येकं दशसंख्यां द्वितीयेपञ्चभिस्तथा ॥५४॥

विशत्यलं तृतीयेहि पञ्चवृद्ध्या दिनेदिने।

कर्तव्यः कुम्भको नित्यं बन्धत्रयसमन्वितः ॥५५॥ - (यो. कुं. उ. 1/54, 55)

All four types of *Kumbhaka* should be practiced in a progressive manner, beginning with ten repetitions on the first day, fifteen on the second day, and twenty on the third day. This pattern should continue, with the number of repetitions increasing by five each day. It is essential that *Kumbhaka* is practiced daily, in conjunction with all three *Bandhas*.

PRECAUTION

Practice should be avoided in polluted environments or during excessively cold weather. Nasal breathing is essential, as it facilitates the natural warming, humidification, and filtration of inhaled air before it reaches the sensitive tissues of the lungs. In contrast, mouth breathing bypasses these protective mechanisms, allowing cold or contaminated air to enter the respiratory tract directly, which may lead to adverse health effects⁹.

CONTRA-INDICATIONS

1. Individuals with hypotension or respiratory conditions such as asthma, bronchitis, or excessive mucus production are advised to refrain from practicing this form of *Kumbhaka*, as it may exacerbate existing symptoms or lead to complications.

2. Individuals with cardiac conditions should perform the practice without incorporating breath retention (*Kumbhaka*), as breath-holding may impose undue stress on the cardiovascular system.
3. This practice is known to reduce the activity of the lower energy centers (*Muladhara* and *Swadhishtan Chakras*), and therefore, individuals with chronic constipation are advised to avoid it, as it may further diminish gastrointestinal motility.
4. In general, this form of *Kumbhaka* is not recommended during the winter season or in cold climatic conditions, as its cooling effects may disrupt the body's thermoregulatory balance.

BENEFITS

Physical benefits:

- 1) The practice induces a cooling effect in the upper digestive tract, particularly in the oral cavity and oesophagus. This cooling sensation may help alleviate hyperacidity and provide relief from inflammatory conditions, such as gastritis and acid reflux.
- 2) The breath-holding phase may transiently inhibit peristaltic movement, leading to a temporary reduction in digestive motility.
- 3) Prolonged stagnation of undigested food produces *Kotha* in intestines, ultimately resulting in release of toxins. *Sheetali* keeps a check on this by increasing peristaltic movement. Therefore, it can be used as a curative measure in *Gulma* and *Udara Roga*.
- 4) *Sheetali* lowers heat in the body which may bring down *Jwara*.
- 5) Foreign bodies and endotoxins are major factors involved in generation of fever. Rate of RBC lysis increases during it. As spleen is 'Graveyard of RBC,' rapid destruction of RBCs causes spleen to work harder than usual and it potentially enlarges. The cooling property of *Sheetali* may regulate the fever which in turn decreases lysis of RBCs and resolves underlying condition.

Psychological benefits:

1. *Sheetali Kumbhaka* activates the parasympathetic nervous system, which facilitates the body's 'rest and digest' response. This shift from sympathetic dominance is associated with a reduction in heart rate and blood pressure, decreased secretion of stress-related hormones, and an overall enhancement in psychological calmness and emotional regulation.
2. Through the combined effects of controlled breathing and breath retention, *Sheetali Kumbhaka* promotes inward-directed awareness and mental stillness states commonly associated with meditative practice. This contributes to enhanced concentration, improved mental clarity, heightened self-awareness, and a reduction in intrusive or distracting thought patterns.
3. Regular practice of *Sheetali Kumbhaka* may enhance vagal tone, which is associated with improved emotional resilience, stabilization of mood, and increased adaptability to psychological stress. These effects may hold therapeutic potential for individuals experiencing mild depressive symptoms or difficulties related to emotional regulation.

Spiritual benefits¹⁰:

1. A primary spiritual benefit of *Sheetali Kumbhaka* is its capacity to regulate and balance the flow of *Prana* (life force energy) within the body. This practice promotes the opening of *Nadis* (subtle energy channels), particularly those in the upper body, resulting in a more even distribution of energy. A balanced flow of *Prana* is considered crucial for spiritual development, as it fosters inner equanimity, enhances mental clarity, and supports the attainment of deeper meditative states.
2. Through its cooling effect and controlled breath, *Śītalī Kumbhaka* is believed to purify the subtle body, particularly the mental and emotional aspects, by removing blockages in the energetic channels (*nāḍīs*) and facilitating alignment with higher states of spiritual consciousness. This purification process is thought to correlate with the activation of higher chakras, particularly the *anāhata chakra* (heart chakra), which is associated with qualities such as love, compassion, and spiritual connection.

DISCUSSION

As time progresses, new diseases emerge due to lifestyle changes. The people tend to follow the western ideas and fall into the trap of an unhealthy lifestyle. *Yogic* principles and concepts are endless, and their application can be useful in the present era for the prevention of disease or for curing the disease. The unification of *Prana* and *Apana* is done at *Hridgranthi* by pulling them together upwards and downwards through *Kumbhaka* and *Mulabandha*. This is called *Pranayama* ^[1]. *Pranayama* practices establish a healthy body by removing blockages in the *Pranamaya kosha*, enabling increased absorption and retention of *Prana*. The practice of *Sheetali kumbhaka* cools the body and affects important brain centres associated with biological drives and temperature regulation. This technique is useful for alleviating psychosomatic disease such as high blood pressure, etc.

CONCLUSION

Pranayamas are a part of *Yogic* practices, and they are an endowment of Indian *Yogic* culture. The long-term practice of *Pranayama* results in astounding benefits that include improving and maintaining human health. *Yoga Shikhopnishat*, *Yoga Kundalini Upnishat* & *Shandilya Upnishat* describe 4 *Kumbhakas*, whereas *Hatharatnavali*, *Hatha Pradipika* & *Gheranda Samhita* mention 8 *Kumbhakas*. *Sheetali Kumbhaka* cools down the body and eradicates numerous diseases like *Ajeerna*, *Gulma*, *Pleeha*, *Jwar*, *Visha*, etc. It may be opined that the practice of *Sheetali Kumbhaka* is a non-invasive method that tackles the suffering caused by the disease and provides a long and healthy life.

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